

INTRODUCING LANGUAGE ASPECT (ENGLISH) TO EARLY CHILDHOOD THROUGH THE COMBINATION OF PICTURE AND PICTURE MODEL, TALKING STICK MODEL, FLASHCARD MEDIA, AND MOVEMENT AND SONG METHOD IN B1 GROUP AT MATAHARIKU BILINGUAL KINDERGARTEN LANDASAN ULIN TENGAH BANJARBARU, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

This paper aims to describe the ability of children to recognize language aspect (English). This paper employed a qualitative approach with Classroom Action Research (CAR) type in two cycles. Each cycle was carried out in two meetings for children in group B1 at Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten with a number of 10 students. The data was collected through teacher observation activity, children's activity and the result of children's ability to recognize the language aspect (English). The result showed that through a combination of Picture and Picture Model, Talking Stick Model, Flashcard Media and Movement and Song Method, it can improve children's ability to recognize language aspect (English). This paper contributes for the teacher as input in combination of method, model, and media to develop aspect of early childhood. Then, for the headmaster which can be used as input in carrying out guidance on teacher to improve the quality of activity in the classroom.

Keywords: language aspect (English), picture and picture model, talking stick model, flashcard media, movement and song method

1. Introduction

Early childhood education is one form of education that focuses on laying the foundation toward physical growth and development (fine and gross motor

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coordination), intelligence (thinking power, creativity, emotional intelligence, and spiritual intelligence), social-emotional (attitude and behavior as well as religion), and language and communication. It is in accordance with the uniqueness and developmental stages of early childhood because each child is different and has their own uniqueness (Sujiyono, 2012).

Mashburn (2008) the development of language skills in kindergarten or preschool in the 0-6 year golden age is very important. Children get language from the family environment and the neighborhood environment through communication as well as the professionalism of the teacher that can increase the interaction that occurs between the teacher and children and the children and friends in school in order to facilitate the readiness of children in learning the language.

Language has a very important role for human life that is as a means of social communication. However, sometimes communication is limited because of the language difference between one country to another. Therefore, it requires an international language that is understood by each country so that communication between countries can run smoothly. One of the International languages is English. English is an international language which is also a language that is widely taught and controlled by many developed countries in the world. The role of English and human resources (teachers) who have the ability to communicate in English as a foreign language in Indonesia are important to be taken into account (Suyanto, 2008).

According to Suyanto (2008), many kindergarten children are introduced to English and grouped into their own group's namely very young learners at the ages of five to seven years. At those ages, children still find it difficult to distinguish concrete things and the abstract. They do not only rely on oral language, but they also must involve the aspects cognitive and body movements. The objects, images or concrete learning activities are not abstract so that children can be interested in getting to know English. And then Klein and Kerstin (2005) stated that the concept of the introduction of English in children in language is that it can be applied to the classification material (color, number, shape, feeling, and family members).

Suyanto (2008) stated that until the age of two years (sensory-motor intelligence intensity stage), children's behavior is still motorized. They do not really understand things that have happened and have not thought conceptually; therefore, the language learning occurs because of the interaction. According to Gusrayani (2014: 8), in introducing English to children from an early age, translating the meaning of a word is not the right way. The teacher can just point to the meaning in question or with something concrete.

Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten is one school that introduce English to children. It is expected that the children are interested in getting to know English. However, in reality in the field, the researchers found that the introduction of aspects of language (English) in early childhood is not optimal. Therefore, most children found it difficult with English because the activities carried out were still abstract and

unattractive. The observation results by the researchers of this study in the group B1 of Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten showed that the children's ability of the language aspects in knowing English is still low. This can be seen from the results of the introduction of aspects of language (English) with the number of 10 children. One child obtained very good developing category (BSB), two children got the developing category according to expectations (BSH), two children got the start developing (MB) category and five children obtained the underdeveloped (BB) category in the language recognition aspect (English). If this problem continues to be left, the children will feel bored in the class. This can occur because the activities carried out are still abstract and unattractive; therefore, the researchers try to design an aspect recognition language (English) for B1 Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten children by using a combination of picture and picture learning models, talking stick model, flashcard media, and movement and song method. The images and songs can make activities become more concrete and make children become interested when the activities take place. Each of the following detail of this employed combination is explained as follows.

Kurniasih & Sani (2016) stated that Picture and Picture model is a cooperative learning model or prioritizes the existence of groups using image media paired or sorted into logical sequences. The advantage of this model is that images are the main factor in achieving development indicators because images are very important to be used to clarify understanding, through pictures of children knowing things that they have never seen.

The talking stick learning model trains children to dare to speak so that the class is more alive and not boring and the children do not become clumsy when the activity is carried out (Kurniasih & Sani, 2016).

The strengths of flashcard media are its function to be both concrete and abstract things, able to overcome the limitations of space, time, and human sensory power, can be used to explain both concrete and abstract problems, easy-to-obtain, cheap (economic value) and easy to use, either individually, in groups, classical, all classes, and schools (Susanto, 2017).

Rachmi, et al. (2008) stated that movement and song proved to be an ideal tool for early childhood to learn in a fun way, and as the best teaching aids for teaching language to early childhood. By singing songs with movement, it can provide satisfaction, joy, and happiness for children so that it encourages children to learn more vigorously (joyful learning). Therefore, by involving the method of motion and song, the activity becomes more enjoyable so that the aspect of language (English) is achieved.

According to Suyanto (2008), all children love singing even though they are shy to sing. Even though they are embarrassed without realizing it, they indirectly recognize a new word in English that is sung in a repetitive motion. Children usually memorize quickly with songs that are simple, cheerful, and easy to say, especially with movement.

Based on the above problems, the researchers are interested in carrying out Classroom Action Research on the children of group B1 in the Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten, Landasan Ulin Tengah, Banjarbaru, entitled "Introducing Language Aspects (English) to Early Childhood Through the Combination of Picture and Picture Model, Talking Stick Model, Flashcard Media, and Movement and Song Method in B1 Group at Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten Landasan Ulin Tengah Banjarbaru". The purpose in this paper to describe: (1) teacher's activity in introducing the language aspects (English) to early childhood through the combination of picture and picture model, talking stick model, flashcard media, and movement and song method in B1 group at Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten Landasan Ulin Tengah Banjarbaru; (2) children's activity in getting to know the language aspects (English) to early childhood through the combination of picture and picture model, talking stick model, flashcard media, and movement and song method in B1 group at Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten Landasan Ulin Tengah Banjarbaru; and (3) children's ability to recognize aspects of language (English) develop through the combination of picture and picture model, talking stick model, flashcard media, and movement and song method in B1 group at Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten Landasan Ulin Tengah Banjarbaru.

2. Methods

This paper was carried out in B1 Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten, Landasan Ulin Tengah, Banjarbaru. Ten children were involved in this paper; seven male students and three female students. The factors studied in this paper were teacher factor, child activity factor, and factor resulting from children's ability to recognize aspects of language (English). The types of data presented in this paper were qualitative and quantitative data. Meanwhile, the data was collected by observing teacher activities, children's activities, and the results of children's ability to recognize aspects of language (English).

The data analysis technique used in this paper was a qualitative analysis to determine the teacher's activity on the recognition of aspects of language (English) through a combination of picture and picture models, talking stick model, flashcard media and movement and song method is said to be successful when it reaches a score of ≥ 27 with a very good criteria. Then, the activities of children in the activity of recognizing aspects of language (English) are said to be successful if each child gets minimum active criteria or reaches a minimum score of ≥ 17 with an overall minimum percentage of $\geq 76\%$. Quantitative analysis to find out the results of the child's ability to recognize aspects of language (English) is said to be successful if the child gets a minimum score on the developing category as expected. Then, the classical success reached $\geq 76\%$ classified as very good development (BSB).

3. Results and Discussion

Based on the results of the analysis in this paper, it was found that the activity of teacher in language recognition activities was carried out very well, the teacher's activities in distracting children who were out of focus (concentration of attention) in order to pay attention to the teacher about the theme to be delivered, prepare the child mentally to be ready to take part in the activity, must know the friendship relationship (close friends) so the teacher must know the child's close friends in the class who can solve the problem when group division, provide motivation to children who are less active by guiding children in group collaboration, motivating children with provide reinforcement so that children are more confident, give awards to children when they can answer questions so that children are motivated to answer questions correctly and correctly, and provide follow-up to what will be done at home related to today's material.

From the results of the data analysis that student activity carried out in cycles I and II reached $\geq 76\%$ or with a very active category with a percentage of 100%. The results of the analysis of the completeness of the children's ability to recognize the English language aspects of children individually in cycle 1 meeting 1, there are two children who have not developed, three children who started developing, and five children developing according to expectation. In the first cycle of meeting 2, there were two children who had not developed, two children began to develop, four children developed according to expectation, and two children developed very well. Then, in cycle II meeting 1, three children began to develop, two children developed according to expectations, and five children developed very well. In the cycle II of meeting 2, two children developed according to expectations and eight children developed very well.

It can be concluded that the result of the children's ability to recognize the English language aspects individually increased from Cycle I to cycle II both at meeting 1 and meeting 2, namely achieving a very active category individually or with a classical percentage of 100%. This shows that there has been an increasing in each meeting so that the ability of children to recognize English language aspects has reached indicators of success. Children's activities from each meeting showed a significant improvement that can be seen from the process of introducing English language aspects through a combination of picture and picture model, talking stick model, flashcard media, and movement and song method.

Then the ability of children to recognize English language aspects classically in the developing category only reached a percentage of 50% and increased at meeting 2 with a percentage of 60%.

Then, the children's ability to recognize the English language aspects has increased from the previous (first) meeting. Meanwhile, in Cycle II meeting 1, it increased with a percentage of 70% and increased again in the Cycle meeting 2 with a percentage of 100%.

It can be concluded that the results of the children's ability to recognize the English language aspects in children increased from Cycle I to cycle II. For Cycle II meeting 2, it has reached the indicator of the success of the introduction of English language aspects $\geq 76\%$ in the category of developing very well with a percentage of 100%.

Therefore, the children are active students. They absorbed all the information that comes to them either intentionally given by people around them or who accidentally come to them. There is an increase in each meeting both from teacher activities, children's activities, and the results of the introduction of English language aspects of children.

In choosing a learning model and strategy, a teacher must also consider the extent to which the learning strategies that will be used can increase the desired abilities of each individual student rather than just considering the aspects of the student group. This is because the essence of learning is to make students in the classroom achieve the desired goals. Developing students' personalities to achieve learning is a goal worth considering in determining the learning strategies to be used (Suriansyah & Aslamiah, 2011). In line with Sanjaya (2012), a teacher is a planner before carrying out the process of activities in the classroom, a teacher must prepare what material to convey, how to deliver it, and what media should be used.

Activities carried out in the classroom by observing principles such as all aspects of children development are interrelated with each other and also influence each other. This development has a sequence because each child has a different development process. Previous experiences of the children also influence subsequent development (adult). It is the development process that can be expected to lead to a more complex, organized and internalized direction, learn from the concrete to the abstract, simple to complex, and verbal movements. This children's development and activities are influenced by diverse cultural and social contexts. In addition, children learn through interaction with peers and adults as well as all their environment. Children as active learners learn with repeated observation, exploration and discovery cycles. Their development is influenced biologically and environmentally, playing as a strategy for children in showing each stage of its development. Children's development will increase if the children are given new skills training and improving the skills they have now. They also have various ways to learn and find out and have various ways to show what they know. Children will learn more easily if they feel safe and comfortable. Children's learning motivation arises when activities are carried out in accordance with children's interests and encourage their great curiosity (Yus, 2014).

Picture and picture model prioritizes the existence of groups using image media that is paired or sorted into logical sequences. This learning model relies on images as media in the development process. These images are a major factor in achieving development indicators (Kurniasih & Sani, 2016).

According to Shoimin (2014) the Talking Stick model is one of the cooperative learning models to which this model is very simple and easy to practice. It is done with the help of a stick. The student who holds the last stick must answer questions from the teacher.

Flashcard media has a positive impact on increasing the ability of children to count at the beginning, this happens when the child must recognize numbers, the process of implementing number concepts so that it is easier for children to understand it more quickly through Flashcard (Susanto, 2017).

According to Suyanto (2008) playing is part of children's daily life and can be used to introduce English to children from an early age, for example involving aspects of mind and body movements such as movement and song method. With movement and song, it has proven to be an ideal tool for early childhood children to learn in a fun way and as the best teaching aids for teaching language to early childhood (Rachmi, et al, 2008).

Early childhood learns through active learning, the method used is to give questions to children and allow thinking / asking themselves, so that the learning outcomes obtained are the construction of the child. Because basically children have the ability to build and create their own knowledge, so it is very important for children to be directly involved in the learning process. Children's learning experiences are more obtained by playing, experimenting with real objects and through concrete experiences. Children have the opportunity to create and manipulate objects or ideas (Sujiono, 2012).

Based on the theory that supports the above increase this occurs because of the accuracy of the teacher in making efforts to improve each meeting in the aspect of language recognition activities (English) by using a combination of picture and picture models, talking stick models, flashcard media and movement and song methods, namely motivate children not to be shy in answering questions from teachers, motivating children to be confident in answering because of the caring and caring motivation of the teacher that makes them not hesitate in doing something. It can be concluded that combination of Picture and Picture model, Talking Stick model, Flashcard media, and Movement and Song method can develop the results of children's ability to recognize English language aspects.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the above discussion, it can be concluded that the teacher's activity introduces the English language aspects of early childhood through a combination of Picture and Picture model, Talking Stick model, Flashcard media and Movement and Song method in group B1 in Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten Banjarbaru is in accordance with the steps that have been planned by obtaining very good categories.

Then, the activities of children in the activity of recognizing English language aspects of early childhood through this model in group B1 in Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten Banjarbaru have increased activity of children with the very active category. The results of the children's ability to recognize the English language aspects through a combination of Picture and Picture model, Talking Stick model, Flashcard media and Movement and Song method in group B1 in Matahariku Bilingual Kindergarten Landasan Ulin Tengah Banjarbaru individually can be said to be successful, which is developing according to expectation, and developing very well. Then, in classical results, the ability of children to recognize English language aspects is very well developed.

This paper contributes for the teacher as input in combination of method, model, and media to develop aspect of early childhood. Then, for the headmaster which can be used as input in carrying out guidance on teacher to improve the quality of activity in the classroom.

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